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TEXT - AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCHS

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Abstract: *This article discusses the text, its categories, ontological features and its constituents (units). First of all, it must be borne in mind that a text is an object of linguistic research. Therefore, the basic concepts of linguistic science should be applied to it. Its initial positions at the present stage of development are based on structural levels. "Only with the help of this concept," writes E. Benveniste, "it is possible to correctly reflect such an essential feature of language as its separative character and the discreteness of its elements. Only the concept of level will help us to discover in all the complexity of forms the originality of the structure of parts and the whole". In this regard, the question arises: is the text a language level?*

Keywords: *text, angle of view, "constructed", "unbuilt", "blurriness", "typology of the text", cohesion, continuum, articulateness of the text.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье обсуждается текст, его категории, онтологические признаки и его конституэнты (единицы). Прежде всего необходимо иметь в виду, что текст — это объект лингвистического исследования. Поэтому к нему следует применять основные понятия лингвистической науки. Ее исходные положения на современном этапе развития зиждется на структурных уровнях. "Лишь с помощью этого понятия, - пишет Э. Бенвенист, - удастся правильно отразить такую существенную особенность языка, как его членоразделительный характер и дискретность его элементов. Только понятие уровня поможет нам обнаружить во всей сложности форм своеобразие строения частей и целого". В связи с этим возникает вопрос: является ли текст уровнем языка?*

Ключевые слова: *текст, угол зрения, "построенные", "непостроенные", "размытость", "типология текста", когезия, континуум, членимость текста.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada matn, uning toifalari, ontologik xususiyatlari va konstitutsiyalari (birliklari) muhokama qilinadi. Avvalo, matn lingvistik tadqiqotlar ob'ekti ekanligini yodda tutish kerak. Shuning uchun unga tilshunoslikning asosiy tushunchalari qo'llanilishi kerak. Rivojlanishning hozirgi bosqichidagi boshlang'ich pozitsiyalari tarkibiy darajalarga asoslanadi. "Faqatgina ushbu kontseptsiya yordamida, - deb yozadi E. Benveniste, - tilning o'ziga xos xususiyati va uning elementlarining diskretligi kabi muhim xususiyatini to'g'ri aks ettirish mumkin. Faqatgina daraja tushunchasi bizga shakllarning barcha murakkabligida qismlar va butun tuzilishning o'ziga xosligini aniqlashga yordam beradi. Shu munosabat bilan savol tug'iladi: matn til darajasimi?*

Kalit so'zlar: *matn, ko'rish burchagi, "qurilgan", "qurilmagan", "loyqalik", "matn tipologiyasi", kogeziya, doimiylik, matn segmenti.*

Introduction. There are different ways to approach the issue of text-researching. From the point of view of the dichotomy of language and speech, i.e., considering language in statics and dynamics, in paradigmatic and syntagmatic terms, it is necessary to recognize that text is not a language level. On the other hand, some parameters of the text give grounds for extrapolating the structure of levels from the axis of paradigmatics to the axis of syntagmatics. Such parameters primarily include the separation of constituent units, the definition of text categories, and the semantic aspect, without which, as is known, analysis of any level cannot do. It follows that the text can be considered as a level, but not of language, but of speech. Speech is also systemic. Even the spontaneity of speech production is not free from the shackles imposed on it by the language system. The text, which, as will be shown below, is a consciously organized result of the speech-making process, obeys certain patterns of organization for it.

Object of study. Recognizing the right of the text to be considered from the standpoint of a level classification (level of speech), we must first determine which units are constituents of the text and which meaningful and formal categories can be found in it. The solutions I have proposed are not the only possible ones, there are probably others with sufficiently reasoned arguments for their recognition. But it can be difficult to put forward arguments against oneself, "one's own point of view" resolutely rejects the possibility of the coexistence of two opposing concepts. Nevertheless, it is precisely in the opposition of concepts that one can see the strengths and weaknesses of one's interpretation of linguistic facts, especially in such a wide field as the linguistics of text. A hypothesis usually arises on the basis of acquired experience. My experience of observing the parameters of the text strongly suggests

the hypothesis that the text is the focus of an organized, ordered, programmed and intrusive random, unprogrammed, arising in the process of its creation.

The general theory of linguistics still pays insufficient attention to the "blurriness", uncertainty and stochasticity in the description of some systemic facts of language, especially when these facts are considered in their functioning. But the "text" itself is such a complex and versatile phenomenon that it becomes necessary to take into account both blurriness, uncertainty, and stochasticity in the process of determining certain systemic, ontological and functional properties of the text. Determinism in the construction of linguistic theory has delayed the progressive movement of our science for a long time. This became especially evident when linguists turned their attention to a text that, by its very nature, is both deterministic and "blurred".

This dual nature of the text has determined the need to find some patterns of text organization. The division of texts into "built" and "unbuilt" appeared, which is proposed by Horst Isenberg. Being in thrall to the ideas of generative grammar, Isenberg believes that it makes no sense to consider the rather vague concept of "typology of text" and that the true subject of text linguistics is the human ability to generate texts.

Used methods. In the proposed article, I try to trace, based on the material of various texts, how separate substantive and formal categories of text function. The reader will not find in it a coherent and consistent theory of the linguistics of the text. Observations have not yet been accumulated enough for such a theory. The schemes, procedures and solutions that we find among various theorists of text linguistics are rather speculative in nature. Everything that is described in this article is a reflection on those phenomena that can rightfully be called text-forming categories. As you know, it is impossible to talk about any object of research, in this case about the text, without naming its categories. The essence of the nomination is that it reveals the understanding of the phenomenon. From a general concept that has not yet been verbally formulated, it becomes scientifically meaningful. The article attempts to explain why these factors have the right to be called grammatical categories. Despite the objections of some guardians of the strictness of grammatical constructions, I interpret the term grammar broadly.

It turned out to be useful to divide the categories of text into meaningful and formal-structural ones, bearing in mind that we combine both of them into grammatical ones. This is necessary because our reflections on these categories are aimed at finding patterns of their functioning, which means that eventually, with the accumulation of a sufficiently large number of facts, it will be possible to compile a grammar of the text. However, the work does not strictly divide into substantive and formal structural

categories: they are very interdependent! Formal structural categories have meaningful characteristics, and meaningful categories are expressed in structural forms. There has not yet appeared in the literature a work that would give in a systematic form the rules for the construction and functioning of text categories. And the categories themselves have not yet been taxonomically processed. It seems to me that thinking is sometimes more useful than postulates. The former allow for a variety of solutions in the process of analyzing the facts of language, while the latter must choose one of the possible approaches, usually leading to a pre-programmed goal.

Many of the categories of text listed in the article, such as informativeness, integration, retrospection, etc., may seem too broad to be recognized only by the text. However, the text in our understanding is a graphical representation of a "piece of reality". He is a product of the written version of the language. The study of an object in scientific and theoretical terms assumes a certain degree of abstraction from specific realizations of this object. In the text, as a result of the speech-making process, it is necessary to identify such features (parameters, signs), on the basis of which it is possible to build some ideal model of this object of research. This is possible only when analyzing a large number of texts related to different functional styles. It is possible to conditionally distinguish from this mass of material texts that more or less approach this ideal model and deviate from it. The definition of the text that I have proposed below refers to an abstract model that allows for a certain variation.

The obtained results and their analysis. One of the essential features of the text is its completeness. This feature pushes the title to the surface of the text, without which, from my point of view, it is impossible to build a text model. True, there are texts without headings - lyrical poems, newspaper reports, letters and some others, but even in them the first sentence — the beginning — usually performs the function of the title, which will be discussed below. Even Russian researchers of our century drew attention to the text as a phenomenon amenable to structuration, i.e., having some patterns of its organization. The works of Bakhtin, Shklovsky, Propp, Tomashevsky and others have still not lost their significance, however, some representatives of the formal structural approach to the text obscured, and sometimes completely ignored the substantive side of the work, without which the structuring of the text is unthinkable.

The starting point in the analysis of a text is the recognition of it as an entity that has a self-sufficient character, but obeys the general laws of the construction of a speech work in its completeness. "For any speech act, first of all, the universal law on the basis of which this utterance is based remains in force, namely the law of the structural organization of this utterance."

Representatives of the Prague Linguistic Circle made a significant contribution to the theory of linguistic analysis of the text. The research of Mathesius, Gavranek,

Vahek, Jedliczka, Gausenblaz and others outlined different approaches to analyzing the structure of the text. Recently, the work of French, German, Dutch and other text theorists has expanded the range of issues related to the structure, ontology and parameters of the text. Among them, it is necessary to mention such prominent scientists as Giro, Greimas, Todorov, Dressler, Van Dyck, Levi-Strass, and Enquist.

A few words about the relationships that arise between the linguistics of the text and stylistics. Many text researchers have long noticed that a number of problems put forward by this branch of knowledge have been considered in some detail by the stylistics of the language. Moreover, the style of the language itself is mainly based on the study of a coherent text. Naturally, therefore, many of the issues raised in this book have already been raised in stylistic studies. It can be said that the stylistics of language serves as an aid to the linguistics of the text in cases where the object of observation is the functional styles of the language and the means that determine them. It is not for nothing that Karel Gzuzenblaz, speaking about speech works, considers style as a "cementing material" and elevates the text to stylistics.

The reader will find here many stylistically relevant facts; they are, as it were, woven into the very structure of the text and determine the originality of what is called meaningful and conceptual information in the book.

Conclusion. The last consideration, which precedes the description of text units and text categories, concerns the very nature of reflections. The interaction of two types (types, features) of the abstract-schematic and concrete-empirical thought process is one of the reliable grounds for a truly scientific knowledge of the studied object. The text, reproducing and describing certain aspects of life (events, characters, relationships, reflections, etc.), is naturally dialectical in nature. Therefore, it is characterized by identity and difference, constancy and variability, linearity and cyclicity. As the text unfolds, there is a gradual accumulation of quantitative information, leading ultimately to a qualitatively new education.

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